

The Effectiveness and Efficiency of Direct Procurement of Office Stationery from a Regional Expenditure Perspective (Case Study of the Regional Inspectorate of Klaten Regency)

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ABSTRACT: Procurement of office stationery is part of the routine operational expenditure of local governments that plays an important role in supporting the smooth implementation of organizational tasks. Although the value of each procurement package is relatively small, the high frequency of procurement causes the accumulation of Office stationery expenditure to be significant and needs to be evaluated from the perspective of effectiveness and efficiency of regional spending. This study aims to analyze the effectiveness and efficiency of direct procurement of Office stationery at the Regional Inspectorate of Klaten Regency in the 2025 Fiscal Year using a value for money approach. This study uses a quantitative descriptive evaluative method with data sourced from procurement documents, budget data and realization of Office stationery expenditure, Office stationery user questionnaires, and limited interviews with procurement officials as supporting data. The results show that direct procurement of Office stationery is in the fairly effective category with an effectiveness index of 79.95 percent, and efficient with an efficiency ratio of 96.14 percent. However, there are still opportunities to improve procurement performance, especially in aspects of timeliness, consistency of needs fulfillment, and price control. Therefore, this study recommends prioritizing e-purchasing mechanisms through e-catalogs for routine and recurring stationery procurement to improve efficiency, transparency, and achieve value for money in regional spending.

KEYWORDS: Direct procurement; office stationery; value for money; e-purchasing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Regional spending is the primary instrument of local governments in carrying out public service functions, development, and strengthening governance. Within the framework of public financial management, regional spending is assessed not only by the size of the budget allocation, but also by the extent to which the budget is managed effectively and efficiently (Purnama et al., 2021). Government organizations engage in two types of logistics: internal logistics, which includes goods necessary for the organization's operations; and external logistics, which includes logistics for individuals, companies, and other institutions. Governments operate externally, providing services to the public (Febrin, 2022).

The shift in performance paradigm toward a public value orientation requires integration between planning, implementation, and results-based evaluation. Local governments need to develop measurement systems that not only assess administrative compliance but also assess the creation of public value as the end result of development policies (Wibowo & Setiawan, 2023). Public sector financial management must be oriented towards value for money, namely achieving the best value through the integration of economic, efficiency, and effectiveness aspects (Nabilah, Moorcy, 2023). Effectiveness relates to the level of achievement of established goals or objectives, while efficiency relates to the comparison between output produced and input used. In the context of regional spending, a value-for-money approach is a crucial foundation for ensuring that every rupiah of the public budget provides maximum benefits to the organization and the community (Mardiasmo, 2018).

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Effectiveness and efficiency are key indicators in assessing government performance. Public sector performance is inextricably linked to the quality of expenditure management, including routine operational expenditures (Nabilah, Moorcy, 2023). Operational expenditures are often considered a less strategic supporting component, yet in practice, they play a crucial role in ensuring the continuity of government organizational activities (Mahmudi, 2025).

One form of routine and recurring operational expenditure is the procurement of office stationery. Stationery procurement generally has a relatively small value per procurement package, so it is often implemented through direct procurement mechanisms. However, the high frequency of procurement throughout the fiscal year results in a significant accumulation of stationery expenditures. This situation makes stationery procurement relevant to study from the perspective of regional spending effectiveness and efficiency (Vladimir, 2020).

In government procurement practices, effectiveness is measured not only by meeting organizational needs, but also by timeliness, conformity to specifications, and support for smooth operations. Public organization performance must be viewed as a system linking goals, processes, and outcomes (Febrin, 2022). Therefore, effective stationery procurement is one that sustainably supports the organization's work processes, not simply fulfilling administrative procedures (Halachmi, Bouckaert, 1995).

The operational efficiency perspective relates to an organization's ability to minimize resource waste without compromising output quality. In the context of stationery procurement, efficiency is reflected in the organization's ability to obtain goods at reasonable prices, utilize the budget optimally, and minimize transaction costs. Stationery procurement that is administratively simple but results in large price variations has the potential to reduce spending efficiency (Robbins, 2016).

Public procurement is a strategic government instrument that serves not only as a mechanism for purchasing goods and services but also as a means of achieving public policy objectives (Thai, 2001). Public procurement regulations are designed to ensure fair competition, transparency, and efficient use of public funds. Therefore, evaluation of procurement practices must consider outcomes, not just compliance with regulations (Arrowsmith, 2010). A budget is an estimate of the achievements to be achieved over a specific timeframe, expressed in financial terms. Therefore, budget planning must be carried out optimally because weak planning can result in underfinancing and overfinancing, which can impact budget effectiveness and efficiency (Hasnita, 2021). The level of budget and spending efficiency is a measure of the success of an activity, assessed based on the amount of costs or resources used to achieve the desired results (Matondang, 2022). The level of effectiveness is a targeted government goal; if achieved successfully, it is considered effective because goals are more valuable than just the amount of money spent.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Concept of Value for Money in Public Spending.

The shift in performance paradigm toward a public value orientation requires integration between planning, implementation, and results-based evaluation. Local governments need to develop measurement systems that not only assess administrative compliance but also assess the creation of public value as the end result of development policies (Wibowo & Setiawan, 2023). Public sector financial management must be oriented towards value for money, namely achieving the best value through the integration of economic, efficiency, and effectiveness aspects (Nabilah, Moorcy, 2023). The value for money approach is a fundamental concept in public sector financial management, emphasizing that every government expenditure must provide the best value for the resources used (Permata, Intan, 2025). Value for money is built on three main pillars: economy, efficiency, and effectiveness. These three aspects are not independent but interrelated in assessing the quality of public spending management (Mardiasmo, 2018).

The economic aspect relates to the government's ability to obtain inputs of adequate quality at the most reasonable price. Efficiency relates to the relationship between inputs and outputs, namely the extent to which the resources used can produce optimal output (Gupta, Kumar, 2021). Meanwhile, effectiveness relates to the level of achievement of predetermined goals or targets. In the context of regional spending, the value for money approach requires that expenditures not only comply with regulations but also generate tangible benefits for the organization and the community (Hartono, Pratiwi, 2019).

That government performance measurement must prioritize effectiveness and efficiency as primary indicators, as both indicators reflect the quality of public resource management (Permata, Intan, 2025). Large expenditures do not necessarily reflect good performance if they are not accompanied by the achievement of objectives and efficient budget utilization. Therefore, value for money is a relevant evaluation framework for assessing regional government operational spending, including the procurement of office stationery (Mahmudi, 2015).

The OECD emphasizes that implementing value for money in public procurement requires a system capable of ensuring transparency, price consistency, and cost control. The OECD also highlights that routine procurements with relatively small values often escape in-depth evaluation, even though they can cumulatively have a significant impact on budget efficiency. Therefore, the procurement of office stationery, as part of operational expenditure, deserves to be evaluated using a value for money approach (OECD, 2019).

2.2. Effectiveness and Efficiency in Public Procurement Performance.

Effectiveness and efficiency are two key concepts in measuring the performance of public sector organizations ([Anderson, Clark, 2020](#)). The performance of public organizations cannot be assessed solely on procedural compliance, but must be seen in terms of the extent to which the organization is able to achieve its stated goals with optimal use of resources. This approach places effectiveness and efficiency as substantive measures of performance ([Halachmi, Bouckaert, 1995](#)). In the context of goods and services procurement, effectiveness relates to the procurement process's ability to meet user needs in a timely manner, according to specifications, and in adequate quantities. Effective procurement is procurement that supports the smooth operation of an organization without disrupting work processes ([Chen, Li, 2022](#)). Emphasizes that operational effectiveness is achieved when an organization's output aligns with established needs and objectives ([Robbins, 2016](#)).

Efficiency, on the other hand, relates to the optimal use of resources to produce those outputs. Efficiency reflects an organization's ability to minimize resource waste, whether in the form of costs, time, or effort ([Van, Weele, 2016](#)). In the procurement of stationery, efficiency can be measured by comparing budgets with actual expenditures, as well as by the consistency of the prices of purchased goods ([Robbins, 2016](#)). The combination of effectiveness and efficiency is an important indicator in assessing procurement performance. Efficient but ineffective procurement, for example, obtaining goods at low prices but not meeting needs, still does not provide optimal value. Conversely, effective procurement that wastes budget also does not reflect good expenditure management. Therefore, evaluation of stationery procurement needs to consider both aspects simultaneously ([Green, Brown, 2023](#)).

2.3. Government Procurement of Goods and Services as a Policy Instrument.

Government procurement of goods and services plays a strategic role in supporting the implementation of public policy ([Prasetyo, Anggraeni, 2020](#)). The public procurement is not merely an administrative activity, but rather a policy instrument that can influence budget efficiency, the quality of public services, and governance. Therefore, procurement must be managed professionally and accountably ([Thai, 2001](#)). Arrowsmith (2010) emphasizes that public procurement regulations are designed to achieve several key objectives, including ensuring fair competition, increasing transparency, and ensuring the efficient use of public funds. Within this framework, procurement evaluation focuses not only on compliance with regulations but also on the outcomes achieved from the procurement process. In practice, government procurement of goods and services involves various methods tailored to specific needs.

2.4. E-Purchasing as an Instrument for Increasing Efficiency and Transparency.

Several previous studies have examined various aspects of e-procurement, demonstrating that LPSE implementation can reduce procurement time by up to 30% compared to conventional systems ([Saputra et al., 2021](#)). Meanwhile, e-Catalog is more effective for procuring low-value standard goods ([Wijaya, 2022](#)). However, these studies have not specifically compared the performance of the two systems in the context of local government, particularly in the environmental sector ([Nguyen & Nguyen, 2023](#)). Advances in information technology have driven the transformation of the public procurement system toward electronic-based procurement. E-purchasing, or e-procurement, is seen as a crucial instrument for increasing procurement efficiency and transparency ([Flynn et al., 2021](#)). E-procurement can reduce transaction costs, accelerate the procurement process, and increase price consistency through standardization ([Croom, Brandon, Jones, 2007](#)).

The success of e-procurement implementation is influenced by organizational readiness, management support, and system integration with user needs ([Kurniawan & Setiawan, 2021](#)). In the context of office stationery procurement, e-purchasing through e-catalogs offers the advantage of providing a list of items with predetermined specifications and prices, thereby reducing the potential for price variation and increasing transparency ([Vaidya et al., 2006](#)).

In Indonesia, the National Agency for the Procurement of Office Supplies developed an e-catalog as part of its e-purchasing system to encourage more accountable and efficient procurement. However, e-purchasing still coexists with direct procurement mechanisms. Therefore, evaluating the performance of direct procurement is crucial to determine the extent to which e-purchasing should be prioritized as an alternative procurement policy.

2.5. Previous Research and Research Position.

Previous research on stationery procurement in Indonesia generally used a qualitative approach with a focus on managerial and procedural aspects. Showed that obstacles to stationery procurement often relate to internal planning and coordination. However, this study did not measure effectiveness and efficiency quantitatively and did not use a value-for-money approach as an analytical framework ([Anggraini et al., 2015](#)).

Unlike previous research, this study positions stationery procurement as part of regional spending that requires quantitative evaluation using effectiveness and efficiency indicators. By integrating a value-for-money approach, this study is expected to provide an empirical contribution to evaluating routine procurement performance and provide an argumentative basis for formulating more efficient and transparent procurement policies.

2.6. Research Hypothesis.

Based on this theoretical framework, the research hypotheses are formulated descriptively as follows:

H1: Direct procurement of office stationery at the Klaten Regency Regional Inspectorate has been implemented effectively based on a value-for-money approach.

H2: Direct procurement of office stationery at the Klaten Regency Regional Inspectorate has been implemented efficiently based on a value-for-money approach.

3. RESEARCH SUBJECTS AND METHODS

- 3.1 Type and Approach. This research uses a descriptive quantitative approach with an evaluative method. The quantitative approach was chosen because this study aims to objectively measure and assess the effectiveness and efficiency of direct procurement of office stationery using measurable indicators. Meanwhile, the evaluative method is used to assess the performance of office stationery procurement based on a value-for-money approach, namely by comparing procurement implementation results against established effectiveness and efficiency criteria. The descriptive approach was used because this study does not aim to test causal relationships between variables or make broad generalizations, but rather to provide an empirical overview of the performance of direct procurement of office stationery in specific work units. Thus, the research results are expected to provide a basis for considering more appropriate procurement policies, particularly in the context of routine procurement within the local government.
- 3.2 Research Object and Location. The object of this research is the direct procurement of office stationery carried out by the Klaten Regency Regional Inspectorate. This research object was selected based on the characteristics of office stationery procurement, which is routine, repetitive, and has a high frequency throughout the fiscal year, thus cumulatively having the potential to impact regional spending efficiency. The research location is the Klaten Regency Regional Inspectorate, a regional agency with an internal oversight function. As an institution that supports good governance, the Inspectorate requires ongoing operational support, including the availability of office stationery. Therefore, an evaluation of office stationery procurement at this agency is relevant to assessing the quality of local government operational expenditure management.
- 3.3 Data Types and Sources. This study used primary and secondary data. Secondary data were obtained from official documents related to the procurement of office stationery for the 2025 Fiscal Year, including: office stationery procurement documents, budget data and actual office stationery expenditures, a list of office stationery procurement packages, and other relevant supporting documents. Secondary data were used to analyze spending efficiency and provide a factual overview of the implementation of direct procurement of office stationery. Primary data were obtained through the distribution of questionnaires to office stationery users at the Klaten Regency Regional Inspectorate. The questionnaires were used to measure user perceptions of the effectiveness of office stationery procurement, specifically regarding timeliness, conformity to specifications, fulfillment of needs, and support for smooth operations. In addition, this study also utilized limited interview data with procurement officials as supporting data. The interviews were conducted semi-structured and served as triangulation to strengthen the interpretation of the quantitative analysis results, rather than as the primary research method.
- 3.4 Data Collection Techniques. Data collection techniques in this study included: 1) Documentation study, which involved reviewing procurement documents and the realization of the 2025 office stationery budget. This technique was used to obtain objective data regarding procurement values, procurement methods, and budget utilization. 2) A questionnaire, developed using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire was distributed to office stationery users to assess the effectiveness of direct procurement of office stationery. 3) Limited interviews, conducted with procurement officials to obtain an overview of office stationery procurement practices, obstacles encountered, and views on the use of e-purchasing. The interview results were used to complement the discussion of the research findings.
- 3.5 Operational Definition of Variables. This study used two main variables: the effectiveness and efficiency of office stationery procurement; 1) The effectiveness of office stationery procurement is defined as the level of ability of direct procurement of office stationery to meet organizational needs in a timely manner, according to specifications, in adequate quantities, and to support smooth operations. Effectiveness is measured through four indicators: timeliness, conformity to specifications, fulfillment of needs, and operational support. 2) Efficiency in office stationery procurement is defined as the level of optimal budget utilization in the procurement of office stationery. Efficiency is measured by comparing the budget and actual expenditure on office stationery in 2025.
- 3.6 Data Analysis Techniques. Data analysis in this study was conducted in several stages; 1) First, questionnaire data was analyzed using descriptive statistics to obtain the average value for each effectiveness indicator. Next, this average value was used to calculate an effectiveness index, which is the ratio between the actual score and the maximum possible score. 2) Second, efficiency analysis was conducted by calculating the expenditure efficiency ratio, which is the comparison between the actual

budget and the established budget. This ratio is used to assess the level of efficiency in stationery procurement in terms of budget utilization. 3) Third, the results of the quantitative analysis were interpreted using effectiveness and efficiency criteria based on a value-for-money approach. Interview data was used as triangulation material to strengthen the discussion and provide context for the quantitative findings.

3.7 Research Analytical Framework. This research's analytical framework is based on a value-for-money approach, focusing on effectiveness and efficiency in evaluating office stationery procurement. The results of the effectiveness and efficiency analysis are then used to assess the performance of direct procurement of office stationery and formulate procurement policy implications, particularly regarding the prioritization of e-purchasing mechanisms as a more efficient and transparent procurement alternative.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overview of Office Stationery Procurement in 2025. Office stationery procurement at the Klaten Regency Regional Inspectorate for the 2025 Fiscal Year was carried out to support the smooth implementation of internal oversight duties and functions. Based on procurement data, the majority of office stationery needs were met through direct procurement mechanisms with relatively small package values. Although the value of each package was not large, the high procurement frequency resulted in significant accumulated office stationery expenditures within a single budget year. This procurement pattern indicates that office stationery is a routine and recurring component of operational expenditures. In the context of value for money, this condition is important to evaluate because poorly managed routine expenditures have the potential to lead to long-term budget inefficiencies. Therefore, an analysis of the effectiveness and efficiency of office stationery procurement was conducted to assess the extent to which current procurement practices have provided the best value for the organization.

4.2 Analysis of the Effectiveness of Direct Procurement of Office Stationery. The effectiveness of office stationery procurement in this study was measured through four indicators: timeliness, conformity to specifications, fulfillment of needs, and support for smooth operations. Measurements were made based on the results of questionnaires filled out by office stationery users, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Effectiveness Index for Direct Procurement of Office Stationery in 2025

Effectiveness Indicator	Average	Index Score (%)	Category
Timeliness	3,76	75,24	Quite effective
Specification Conformity	4,11	82,29	Effective
Need Fulfillment	3,98	79,62	Quite effective
Operational Support	4,13	82,67	Effective
Total Effectiveness Index	–	79,95	Quite effective

Source: Processed Data, 2025.

Based on Table 1, the effectiveness level of direct procurement of stationery is categorized as moderately effective, with an effectiveness index of 79.95 percent. The indicators of conformity to specifications and operational support are categorized as effective, indicating that the purchased stationery generally meets the technical needs of users and supports smooth work activities. However, the indicators of timeliness and fulfillment of needs remain categorized as moderately effective. This indicates that although stationery procurement has been able to meet the organization's overall needs, there are still limitations in terms of timely provision and consistent fulfillment of needs. This finding indicates the need for more systematic planning of office stationery needs so that procurement can be carried out more timely and equitably across work units.

4.3. Efficiency Analysis of Office Stationery Procurement. The efficiency of office stationery procurement was analyzed by comparing the allocated budget with the actual expenditure on office stationery for Fiscal Year 2025. The calculation results indicate that the efficiency ratio is categorized as efficient, meaning that the actual expenditure did not exceed the allocated budget. The results of the efficiency analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Efficiency of Office Stationery Procurement Budget in 2025

Year	Budget (Rp)	Realization (Rp)	Efficiency Ratio (%)	Category
2025	232.739.514	223.746.850	96,14	Efficiency

Source: Processed Data, 2025.

Based on Table 2, the efficiency ratio for office stationery procurement was 96.14 percent, which falls into the efficient category. This result indicates that actual office stationery spending did not exceed the established budget, so overall, budget utilization can be considered efficient. However, the efficiency ratio, which remains close to 100 percent, indicates that potential budget savings can still be increased. From an efficiency perspective, Mahmudi (2015) emphasized that efficiency is not only measured by avoiding budget wastage, but also by the extent to which an organization is able to minimize costs for the same output.

4.4 Synthesis of Stationery Procurement Analysis from a Value-for-Money Perspective. To provide a more comprehensive picture, the results of the analysis of the effectiveness and efficiency of stationery procurement are synthesized from a value-for-money perspective, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Synthesis of Office Stationery Procurement Analysis from a Value for Money Perspective

Value for Money Aspect	Key Findings	Implications
Effectiveness	Quite effective (79,95%)	Needs to improve timeliness and consistency in meeting needs
Efficiency	Efficient (96.14%)	Still has opportunities for budget savings.
Transparency	Price variations between packages	Direct procurement dominance mechanism.
Mechanism	Dominance of direct procurement	E-purchasing needs to be prioritized.

Source: Processed Data, 2025.

Based on the synthesis in Table 3, it can be concluded that direct procurement of office supplies has provided a fairly good level of effectiveness and efficiency, but is not yet fully optimal from a value-for-money perspective. The dominance of repeated direct procurement leads to price variations and limitations in cost control. Therefore, optimizing the e-purchasing mechanism through e-catalogs is a relevant policy alternative to improve efficiency, transparency, and accountability in office stationery procurement.

5.5 The Role of E-Purchasing as an Alternative Procurement Policy. Interviews with procurement officials indicate that direct procurement is chosen for its convenience and flexibility in meeting urgent needs. However, informants also stated that the e-purchasing mechanism through e-catalogs offers advantages in terms of transparency and price uniformity. These findings align with research by Croom and Brandon-Jones (2007), which states that e-procurement can increase efficiency through price standardization and reduced transaction costs. Furthermore, Vaidya et al. (2006) emphasized that effective e-procurement implementation can strengthen procurement governance and reduce the risk of inefficiency. In the context of office stationery procurement, e-purchasing offers the opportunity to consolidate routine needs and obtain more competitive prices. Therefore, this study suggests that e-purchasing deserves priority as a strategy to increase value for money in office stationery procurement.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the effectiveness and efficiency of direct procurement of office stationery at the Klaten Regency Inspectorate for the 2025 Fiscal Year, it can be concluded that the implementation of office stationery procurement has been quite effective and efficient in supporting the smooth operation of the organization. This is reflected in the effectiveness index value of 79.95 percent, which falls into the moderately effective category, and the budget efficiency ratio of 96.14 percent, which falls into the efficient category. In terms of effectiveness, office stationery procurement has been able to provide goods that meet specifications and support general operational activities. However, several indicators, particularly timeliness and consistency of fulfillment, still fall into the moderately effective category. This condition indicates that office stationery needs planning has not been fully integrated with the procurement cycle, resulting in procurement not being able to be implemented optimally in some situations. In terms of efficiency, the realization of office stationery spending that did not exceed the budget indicates that budget management has been carried out quite well. However, price variations between procurement packages indicate that there are still opportunities for efficiency improvements, particularly through more consistent and standardized price controls. From a value-for-money perspective, direct procurement of office stationery meets the principles of effectiveness and efficiency to an adequate level, but is not yet fully optimal. The dominant use of direct procurement mechanisms for routine and recurring needs has the potential to limit the achievement of maximum efficiency and transparency.

Implications of Research Findings. The findings of this study have practical implications for the management of office stationery procurement within local governments. First, planning for office stationery needs needs to be conducted more systematically to improve timeliness and fulfillment of needs. Second, procurement mechanisms need to be directed towards increasing price consistency to strengthen budget efficiency. Third, optimizing e-purchasing can be a strategic step to increase transparency and accountability in office stationery procurement.

Recommendations. First, improved planning of office stationery needs needs to be carried out in a more systematic and integrated manner. Preparing a more accurate and scheduled office stationery needs plan is expected to improve procurement timeliness and ensure more consistent fulfillment of needs across work units. Second, optimizing the e- purchasing mechanism through the e- catalog needs to be prioritized for routine and recurring office stationery procurement. E-purchasing offers advantages in terms of price standardization, process transparency, and reduced price variation between procurement packages. Thus, the use of e- purchasing is expected to increase spending efficiency and strengthen the principle of value for money. Third, direct procurement can still be used selectively for urgent needs or needs that are not available in the e-catalog. However, their use must be limited and accompanied by price controls and adequate documentation to maintain accountability and efficiency. Fourth, regular monitoring and evaluation of office stationery procurement is necessary to ensure that the implemented procurement policy has a positive impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of regional spending. Periodic evaluations can also serve as a basis for improving procurement policies in the future.

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